

CLINICAL OUTCOMES OF INTRAVESICAL CHEMOTHERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH HIGH-RISK NON-MUSCLE INVASIVE BLADDER CANCER

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Relevance:

Non-muscle invasive bladder cancer (NMIBC) is characterized by a high recurrence rate and risk of progression. In settings where Bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG) immunotherapy is not available, intravesical chemotherapy remains the cornerstone of adjuvant treatment. However, data comparing different chemotherapeutic agents in routine practice remain limited.

Objective:

To assess the efficacy, tolerability, and comparative outcomes of intravesical chemotherapy regimens in patients with high-risk NMIBC following TURBT.

Materials and Methods:

This prospective study included 80 patients with high-risk NMIBC (Ta-T1, G3 and/or CIS) treated between 2022 and 2025. After complete TURBT, patients received intravesical chemotherapy with mitomycin C (n=32), doxorubicin (n=26), or epirubicin (n=22). Induction schedules consisted of 6–8 weekly instillations, followed by monthly maintenance for up to 1 year. Follow-up included cystoscopy and urinary cytology every 3 months during the first 2 years and every 6 months thereafter. Endpoints were recurrence-free survival (RFS), progression-free survival (PFS), and treatment-related adverse events. Statistical analysis applied Kaplan–Meier survival estimates and log-rank tests.

Results:

• **Recurrence:** Detected in 24 patients (30%). By regimen: mitomycin C – 21.9% (7/32), doxorubicin – 34.6% (9/26), epirubicin – 40.9% (9/22), $p=0.04$. Median time to recurrence was 11 months.

• **Progression:** Occurred in 10 patients (12.5%). Rates: mitomycin C – 6.3% (2/32), doxorubicin – 11.5% (3/26), epirubicin – 18.2% (4/22). Two-year PFS was 87.5% overall, but only 72% in the epirubicin group.

• **Survival outcomes:** Two-year RFS: 74% in mitomycin C, 62% in doxorubicin, and 59% in epirubicin groups. Patients treated with mitomycin C demonstrated the most favorable oncological outcomes.

• **Adverse events:** Local complications were reported in 15 patients (18.7%), including chemical cystitis (12.5%) and dysuria (6.2%). Grade II hematuria occurred in 3 patients (3.7%). No systemic toxicity or treatment discontinuation was observed.

• **Comparative efficacy:** Mitomycin C showed superior disease control compared with doxorubicin and epirubicin, although tolerability was similar across regimens.

Conclusion:

Intravesical chemotherapy is an effective and safe strategy for high-risk NMIBC in the absence of BCG immunotherapy. Mitomycin C demonstrated the best recurrence and progression outcomes among the studied regimens, while all drugs were well tolerated. Refining chemotherapy protocols and maintenance schedules could further improve long-term outcomes.

Keywords: Non-muscle invasive bladder cancer, intravesical chemotherapy, mitomycin C, doxorubicin, epirubicin, recurrence, progression

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